

In attempts to describe the attitude towards such an amazing creation of the human intellect as quantum mechanics, the word “duality” unconditionally wins. Indeed, on the one hand, its impeccably tuned mathematical apparatus makes it possible to carry out calculations with great accuracy to predict the behavior of objects in the microworld.

On the other hand, it is difficult to get rid of the vague feeling of the almost complete lack of classical clarity of their figurative representation .

The thought experiment, invented by one of the founders of quantum physics, E. Schrodinger , is intended to demonstrate the incompleteness of the general theory of physics. Schrödinger wanted to show that physics is not may describe the transition from microsystems , or quantum systems to macrosystems.

Schrödinger describes his thought experiment this way:

A certain cat is locked in a steel chamber with the following infernal machine (which must be protected from the cat's direct intervention): inside a Geiger counter there is a tiny amount of radioactive substance, so small that only one atom can decay in an hour, but with the same probability that and not fall apart; if this happens, the reading tube is discharged and the relay is activated, releasing the hammer, which breaks the flask with hydrocyanic acid.

If we leave this entire system to itself for an hour, then we can say that the cat will be alive after this time, as long as the atom does not disintegrate. The very first disintegration of the atom would poison the cat. The psi-function of the system as a whole will express this by mixing or smearing a living and a dead cat in equal parts.

What is typical in such cases is that uncertainty originally limited to the atomic world is transformed into macroscopic uncertainty, which can be eliminated by direct observation. This prevents us from naively accepting the blur model as reflecting reality.

The contradiction between macroscopic reality and the blur model indicated by Schrödinger requires explanation. If in the macrocosm we cannot accept the idea of the blurred state of a cat, then what then is the nature of macroscopic uncertainty? What is the meaning of the words blurriness and smearing here? Where does the experimenter get the image of blurriness and blurriness of the object under study, which is a cat?

Observation is a universal method of research and knowledge of the material world, its objects, components, properties. But Schrödinger’s experiment contains an example of how a researcher enters into a relationship with the world that is alternative to the relationship to observe or be observed.

This relationship arises in the case when some object is fundamentally unobservable, but the cognizing subject is forced to judge, reflect, reason about it. Therefore, in the system described by Schrödinger, it is necessary to postulate the existence of an object that, according to serious theoretical or indirect empirical considerations and observations, may have objective existence, but will never and under no circumstances be amenable to direct observation. Let us call such an object ideal, as opposed to observable (material) objects.

Perhaps a physicist will be disgusted by an attempt to introduce into consideration an entity that does not relate to physical reality, but reflects the activity of the researcher, and therefore is subjective in nature.

The question of the objectivity of the ideal is of a philosophical nature and methodologically important for those sciences that are based on empirical knowledge. First of all, there are objectively attempts to express the ideal in symbolic form, using words and other linguistic units: idea, thought, concept, representation, judgment, information, information, meaning, semantics, etc.

These linguistic units have a vague meaning, which is expressed, revealed, manifested in the presence of a large number of definitions (for example, the concept of “concept”) or in the impossibility of giving a more or less precise definition. In the absence of definitions, this vocabulary is also used, and in the contexts of its use, judgments, ideas, metaphors about it, created by those who use this vocabulary, are expressed.

These judgments, ideas, metaphors are different, and this is also an objective fact that we can observe in different conditions of communication. Therefore, none of the means of expressing the ideal can express the only true understanding of the ideal or the only true judgment about it. In particular, a characteristic understanding of ideal entities is their conceptualization as material objects.

Let's return to Schrödinger's cat. In the description of this experiment there is an ideal object - a thought, concept, idea, etc. about the state of the cat. As soon as we begin to talk (judge, reason, think) about this object, we name it. Such a name is, for example, the phrase state of a cat.

About this state one can make alternative hypothetical judgments: the cat is alive and the cat is dead, expressed by the corresponding sentences of the language. The state of the cat is not observed in the physical world, because these are the conditions of the experiment. The state of a cat as an idea, concept, representation is not observed in principle, because this is a property of ideal objects.

Only linguistic, speech, means that are names of ideal objects or expressing judgments are observed. If you open the chamber in which the cat is located, then you can directly observe the state of the cat, i.e., a new observable object appears (a living or dead cat), but the existence of an unobservable ideal object, about which we have previously judged, reasoned, and thought, ceases.

Ideal objects are not observed, but their manifestations are observed. This statement seems very important from a methodological point of view, since this property of the ideal allows it to be analyzed using physical methodology, using observation.

Schrödinger's cat is an ideal-material system that consists of observable physical objects and an ideal object - the state of a cat, which we do not observe, but about which we only judge, think, reason.

Thanks to the expressiveness (verbalization) of an ideal object, it is possible to apply approaches to it similar to those that physicists use when studying material systems. In particular, this ideal object is characterized by a degree of uncertainty, which is expressed in the possibility of making

different judgments about the state of the cat and which depends on the number of probable states.

Why is the experiment itself considered as a material part of the system? After all, the experiment is also a mental one. It exists in our imagination, just like the state of the cat before the camera was opened. However, there is a fundamental difference between the experiment and the cat's condition.

An experiment, its structure and the conditions for its occurrence are a made decision that does not imply uncertainty, hypotheticalness and variability. If we were considering the process of engineering implementation of an experiment, then at different stages of this activity we would have to deal with a problematic situation that implies uncertainty.

The canonical description of the experiment proposes a mechanism that assumes only two alternatives to the cat's state. Let us assume that this state is judged by an outside observer who did not participate in the preparation of the experiment.

Then it may turn out that there is also a third alternative - the cat is missing. Here we are dealing with such an objectively existing phenomenon as the activity of the participants in the experiment. The specific features of this activity may vary. Maybe the experimenters felt sorry for the cat and did not put it in danger, or maybe they wanted to play a prank on the observer.

A situation is possible when some participants in the experiment conducted this experiment and learned about the state of the cat, while others did not participate in opening the chamber with the cat and do not know about the results of the experiment. Then for some experimenters the ideal object continues to exist, but for others it has disappeared, replaced by a material object - a living, dead cat or an empty chamber.

From these assumptions it is clear that the existence of an ideal object is inseparable from the activities of people. The connection between ideal objects and activity is an objective phenomenon, and from the point of view of the researcher it is a cognitive, psychological, social problem.

In literature there is one very emotional, artistic, and at the same time, surprisingly accurate and understandable description of the Schrödinger paradox. It is cited by the modern French writer Jean-Philippe Toussaint in his novel *Monsieur*, and it is completely unimportant, although it is noteworthy in its own way, that in the quoted passage it is a cat, not a cat, that is locked in the device: ... the cat is placed in a closed space where a test tube is installed with potassium cyanide and a detector with a radioactive atom;

if the atom splits, the detector triggers a mechanism that breaks the test tube and kills the cat... The probability that the above atom will decay within an hour is fifty percent.

The problem asks: will the cat be alive or dead in sixty minutes? There are only two options. ... However, according to the Copenhagen School, a cat in an hour will be neither alive nor dead, with equal chances of surviving or dying. You say, you can look in and check without harming the experiment, because a cat will not die from one glance and will not come back to life if it has already died.

Meanwhile, again, according to Copenhagen, one single glance radically changes the mathematical description of its condition, since from neither alive nor dead the cat will turn into either definitely alive or completely dead: it depends on your luck.

In the correspondence between Einstein and de Broglie there is a statement that the wave function is fundamentally monochromatic. If it is recognized as valid for the cat object, then this paradox loses its meaning altogether.

Indeed, in this case, there can be no question of any superposition of the cat's states, and one can, with relief and a clear conscience, exclaim: Hurray! Finally, Schrödinger's long-suffering cat has been saved, definitely alive and free!

The thought physical experiment of Schrödinger's cat is a simple example of a material-ideal system, the analysis of which makes it possible to explain the contradiction between the clarity of macroscopic reality and the idea of the blurriness of a material object that arises in the experimenter as a result of research activities.